

Dataset Annotation Guidelines:

- Use the sense definitions provided in the Oromo-English Dictionary (Gamta, 1989) as the primary annotation reference.
- Read the entire sentence to understand the contextual meaning before assigning a sense label.
- Assign exactly one sense label to each annotated target word based on its contextual meaning.
- For cases where the correct sense is unclear, consult the dictionary definitions and resolve disagreements through discussion between the annotators.
- Apply the same annotation criteria consistently across all sentences to ensure semantic consistency and annotation reliability.